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A BP NEURAL NETWORK BASED ON IMPROVED PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION FOR SOLVING OPTIMAL REACTIVE POWER DISPATCH PROBLEM

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Abstract

This paper presents an algorithm for solving the multi-objective reactive power dispatch problem in power system. The basic Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm and its principle have been introduced, the Particle Swarm Optimization has low accelerate speed and can be easy to fall into local extreme value, so the Particle Swarm Optimization based on the improved inertia weight is presented. This method means using nonlinear decreasing weight factor to change the fundamental ways of PSO. To allow full play to the approximation capability of the function of BP neural

network and overcome the main shortcomings of its liability to fall into local extreme value and the study proposed a concept of applying improved PSO algorithm and BP network jointly to optimize the original weight and threshold value of network and incorporating the improved PSO algorithm into BP network to establish a improved PSO-BP network system. This method (BP-IPSO) improves convergence speed and the ability to search optimal value. We apply the improved particle swarm algorithm to reliability prediction. Compared with the traditional BP method, this kind of algorithm can minimize errors and improve convergence speed at the same time. In order to evaluate

the proposed algorithm, it has been tested on IEEE 30 bus system and compared to other algorithms and simulation results show that (BP-IPSO) is more efficient than others for solution of single-objective ORPD problem.

Keywords: BP improvement, neural network, reliability prediction, the improved PSO, optimal reactive power, Transmission loss.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Optimal reactive power dispatch problem is one of the difficult optimization problems in power systems. The sources of the reactive power are the generators, synchronous condensers, capacitors, static compensators and tap changing transformers. The problem that has to be solved in a reactive power optimization is to determine the required reactive generation at various locations so as to optimize the objective function. Here the reactive power dispatch problem involves best utilization of the existing generator bus voltage magnitudes, transformer tap setting and the output of reactive power sources so as to minimize the loss and to enhance the voltage stability of the system. It involves a non linear optimization problem. Various mathematical techniques have been adopted to solve this optimal reactive power dispatch problem. These include the gradient method [1,2], Newton method [3] and linear programming [4-7].The gradient and Newton methods suffer from the

difficulty in handling inequality constraints. To apply linear programming, the input-output function is to be expressed as a set of linear functions which may lead to loss of accuracy. Recently Global Optimization techniques such as genetic algorithms have been proposed to solve the reactive power flow problem [8.9]. In recent years, the problem of voltage stability and voltage collapse has become a major concern in power system planning and operation. To enhance the voltage stability, voltage magnitudes alone will not be a reliable indicator of how far an operating point is from the collapse point [10]. The reactive power support and voltage problems are intrinsically related. Hence, this paper formulates the reactive power dispatch as a multi-objective optimization problem with loss minimization and maximization of static voltage stability margin (SVSM) as the objectives. The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [14,15,21] , proposed by Kennedy and Eberhart (1995), Eberhart and Kennedy (1995) and Eberhart and Shi (2001), was based on the optimal algorithm of swarm intelligence and It guides optimal search through swarm intelligence producing by the corporation and competition among particles. Because the algorithms has the virtues of the simple principle, the easy realization, prompt self-optimized paces and robustness, now it has been widely used in function optimization, neural works, fuzzy system control and so on. However, in early stage, the searching speed is fast, but later it becomes slower. Particle swarm shows intensive similarity, thus falling into local optimum. The artificial Neural Network possesses the ability of processing database in parallel, organizing and learning by itself. It has made great achievements in many fields. Especially neural network technique has been used in reliability and few researchers apply the method [16,20,23] to predict failures (Ying-Jie and Chang-Hua, 2005; Hai-Dong *et al.*, 2003; Jin-Yong *et al.*, 2004). Theoretically, BP Neural Network may approach any continual nonlinear function. However, affected greatly by the sample, it may fall into local minimum value, thus it can't ensure that it converge the minimum value in overall situations.

Therefore, current research emphasis has been on optimal improvement of BP Neural Network. Recently, PSO algorithm is introduced into BP network optimization by using iterate algorithm of particle swarm instead of gradient correction algorithm of BP network. This method can shorten the time of training network and improve the convergence speed of BP algorithm. However, according to different system object, if basic particle swarm algorithm is modified, the performance of BP network is improved and its practicality is better. For balancing between the global search and the local search and improving the precision of the result, this study proposed the nonlinear strategies for decreasing inertia weight based on the idea of the existing linear decreasing inertia weight. The result of simulation shows that the optimizing methods speed the rapidity of convergence obviously and the precision of simulation increase greatly. The performance of (BP-IPSO) has been evaluated in standard IEEE 30 bus test system and the results analysis shows that our proposed approach outperforms all approaches investigated in this paper.

II. VOLTAGE STABILITY EVALUATION

A. Modal analysis for voltage stability evaluation

Modal analysis is one of the methods for voltage stability enhancement in power systems. The linearized steady state system power flow equations are given by.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P \\ \Delta Q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} J_{P\theta} & J_{PV} \\ J_{Q\theta} & J_{QV} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \theta \\ \Delta V \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where

ΔP = Incremental change in bus real power.

ΔQ = Incremental change in bus reactive Power injection

$\Delta \theta$ = incremental change in bus voltage angle.

ΔV = Incremental change in bus voltage Magnitude

$J_{P\theta}$, J_{PV} , $J_{Q\theta}$, J_{QV} jacobian matrix are the sub-matrixes of the System voltage stability is affected by both P and Q.

However at each operating point we keep P constant and evaluate voltage stability by considering incremental relationship between Q and V.

To reduce (1), let $\Delta P = 0$, then.

$$\Delta Q = [J_{QV} - J_{Q\theta}J_{P\theta}^{-1}J_{PV}]\Delta V = J_R\Delta V \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta V = J^{-1} - \Delta Q \quad (3)$$

Where

$$J_R = (J_{QV} - J_{Q\theta}J_{P\theta}^{-1}J_{PV}) \quad (4)$$

J_R is called the reduced Jacobian matrix of the system.

B. Modes of Voltage instability:

Voltage Stability characteristics of the system can be identified by computing the eigen values and eigen vectors

Let

$$J_R = \xi \wedge \eta \quad (5)$$

Where,

ξ = right eigenvector matrix of J_R

η = left eigenvector matrix of J_R

$\wedge$ = diagonal eigenvalue matrix of J_R and

$$J_R^{-1} = \xi \wedge^{-1} \eta \quad (6)$$

From (3) and (6), we have

$$\Delta V = \xi \wedge^{-1} \eta \Delta Q \quad (7)$$

or

$$\Delta V = \sum_i \frac{\xi_i \eta_i}{\lambda_i} \Delta Q \quad (8)$$

Where ξ_i is the ith column right eigenvector and η the ith row left eigenvector of J_R .

λ_i is the ith eigen value of J_R .

The ith modal reactive power variation is,

$$\Delta Q_{mi} = K_i \xi_i \quad (9)$$

where,

$$K_i = \sum_j \xi_{ij}^2 - 1 \quad (10)$$

Where

ξ_{ji} is the jth element of ξ_i

The corresponding ith modal voltage variation is

$$\Delta V_{mi} = [1/\lambda_i] \Delta Q_{mi} \quad (11)$$

In (8), let $\Delta Q = e_k$ where e_k has all its elements zero except the k th one being 1. Then,

$$\Delta V = \sum_i \frac{\eta_{1k} \xi_1}{\lambda_1} \quad (12)$$

η_{1k} k th element of η_1

V-Q sensitivity at bus k

$$\frac{\partial V_k}{\partial Q_k} = \sum_i \frac{\eta_{1k} \xi_1}{\lambda_1} = \sum_i \frac{P_{ki}}{\lambda_1} \quad (13)$$

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The objectives of the reactive power dispatch problem considered here is to minimize the system real power loss and maximize the static voltage stability margins (SVSM).

A. Minimization of Real Power Loss

Minimization of the real power loss (Ploss) in transmission lines of a power system is mathematically stated as follows.

$$P_{loss} = \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{j=(i,j)} G_k (V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2V_i V_j \cos \theta_{ij}) \quad (14)$$

Where n is the number of transmission lines, G_k is the conductance of branch k , V_i and V_j are voltage magnitude at bus i and bus j , and θ_{ij} is the voltage angle difference between bus i and bus j .

B. Minimization of Voltage Deviation

minimization of the Deviations in voltage magnitudes (VD) at load buses is mathematically stated as follows.

$$\text{Minimize VD} = \sum_{k=1}^{nl} |V_k - 1.0| \quad (15)$$

Where nl is the number of load busses and V_k is the voltage magnitude at bus k .

C. System Constraints

Objective functions are subjected to these constraints shown below.

Load flow equality constraints:

$$P_{Gi} - P_{Di} - V_i \sum_{j=1}^{nb} v_j \begin{bmatrix} G_{ij} & \cos \theta_{ij} \\ +B_{ij} & \sin \theta_{ij} \end{bmatrix} = 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, nb \quad (16)$$

$$Q_{Gi} - Q_{Di} - V_i \sum_{j=1}^{nb} v_j \begin{bmatrix} G_{ij} & \cos \theta_{ij} \\ +B_{ij} & \sin \theta_{ij} \end{bmatrix} = 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, nb \quad (17)$$

where, nb is the number of buses, P_G and Q_G are the real and reactive power of the generator, P_D and Q_D are the real and reactive load of the generator, and G_{ij} and B_{ij} are the mutual conductance and susceptance between bus i and bus j .

Generator bus voltage (V_{Gi}) inequality constraint:

$$V_{Gi}^{min} \leq V_{Gi} \leq V_{Gi}^{max}, i \in ng \quad (18)$$

Load bus voltage (V_{Li}) inequality constraint:

$$V_{Li}^{min} \leq V_{Li} \leq V_{Li}^{max}, i \in nl \quad (19)$$

Switchable reactive power compensations (Q_{Ci}) inequality constraint:

$$Q_{Ci}^{min} \leq Q_{Ci} \leq Q_{Ci}^{max}, i \in nc \quad (20)$$

Reactive power generation (Q_{Gi}) inequality constraint:

$$Q_{Gi}^{min} \leq Q_{Gi} \leq Q_{Gi}^{max}, i \in ng \quad (21)$$

Transformers tap setting (T_i) inequality constraint:

$$T_i^{min} \leq T_i \leq T_i^{max}, i \in nt \quad (22)$$

Transmission line flow (S_{Li}) inequality constraint:

$$S_{Li}^{min} \leq S_{Li} \leq S_{Li}^{max}, i \in nl \quad (23)$$

Where, nc , ng and nt are numbers of the switchable reactive power sources, generators and transformers.

IV. THE OPTIMAL ALGORITHM OF PARTICLE SWARM

The optimal algorithm of improved particle swarm is not dependent of fields of problems. However, it uses the code of decision variable as operation object and adaption function as searching objects. Furthermore, it can use the information

from various searching points. It applies to solve the problem about nonlinearity and non-differentiable function and multiple objectives. It has been applied to many scientific fields (Jin-Yong *et al.*, 2004; Xiang *et al.*, 2008; Jie-Ping *et al.*, 2009), but it still has many problems.

The optimal algorithm of basic particle swarm: Supposing in the D-dimensional objects searching space, there is a community composed of N particle. The “i” particle represent a D-dimensional vector,

$X_i = (X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{id})$ It means that the “i” particle represents its position in this space. Every position of particle “X” is a potential solution. If we put “x” into objective function, we can know the adaptive value. We can know whether the “x” is the optimal answer based on the adaptive value. The speed of particle is also a D-dimensional, it also recorded as $v_i = (v_{i1}, v_{i2}, \dots, v_{id})$. We record the particle I to the h times, the optimal position was $P_i = (P_{i1}, P_{i2}, \dots, P_{id})$. All the particles to the h times, the optimal position was $P_{gd} = (P_{g1}, P_{g2}, \dots, P_{gd})$. The basic formulas are as follows:

$$v_{id}^{t+1} = wv_{id}^t + c_1r_1^t(P_{id}^t - x_{id}^t) + c_2r_2^t(P_{gd}^t - x_{id}^t) \quad (24)$$

$$x_{id}^{t+1} = x_{id}^t + v_{id}^{t+1} \quad (25)$$

Where, c_1 & c_2 : Speeding coefficient, adjusting the maxim step length that flying the best particle in whole situation and the individual best particle respectively. Appropriate c_1 and c_2 speed up the convergence and avoid falling into partial optimality r_1 & r_2 : Random number between 0 and 1, for controlling the weight of speed W: Inertia factor. It was oriented toward overall searching .We usually take the original value as 0.9 and make it to 0.1 with the addition and reduction of the times of iteration. It mainly used to total

searching, making the searching space converge to a certain space. Then we can get the solution in high degree of accuracy by partial refined researching (Yi-Shan *et al.*, 2009). The optimal algorithm of improved particle swarm: With the increasing number of dimension of problems, basic PSO algorithm is easily falling into partial extreme value, thus influence the optimal function of algorithm. Someone brought up with improved algorithm. Many scholars’ research shows [17,24,25,27,28] that “w has a great influence on the algorithm of particle swarm (Xiao-Rong and Shu-Xian, 2008; Hao and Xiao-Lei, 2008). When the “w” is bigger, the algorithm has a strong ability in total searching and when the “W” is smaller, it is good for partial searching. “Therefore, in recent years, some scholars brought up many schemes (Jiang-Hong *et al.*, 2006; Xuan *et al.*, 2009). According to formula (2), literature (Jiang-Hong *et al.*, 2006) came up with LDW (Linearly Decreasing Inertia Weight) that is

$$W = W_{max} - \frac{t \times (W_{max} - W_{min})}{t_{max}} \quad (26)$$

where, W_{max} & W_{min} : The maximum and minimum value of W , t : The step of iteration , t_{max} : The maximum iteration step.

However, there are still problems in formula (26). In the primary period of operation, if it detects the optimal point, it wants to converge to the optimal point promptly. However, the linear reduction slows down the speed of convergence of algorithm. In the later period of function, with the reduction of “w”, it may make the ability of total searching decline and the variety awaken. Finally it may easily fall into partial optimum (Xiu-Ye and Hong-Xia, 2010). In this text, we use the PSO method of nonlinear variation weight with

momentum to improve this method. That is:

$$w = w_{max} - \frac{t \times (w_{max} - w_{min})}{2^{\theta} t_{max}} \quad (27)$$

2^{θ} is momentum, when in $\theta = t/t_{max}$, t is smaller, 2^{θ} is near to 1 and w is near to w_{max} , it ensure the ability of total searching.. With the increasing of t , w reduces in non linearity, ensuring the searching ability in partial areas. In the later period ($t = t_{max}$), avoiding the problems caused by the decrease of w . That is, the reduction ability of total searching and the decline of variety.

V. THE IMPROVED PSO-BP ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK ALGORITHM

BP neural network: The standard BP Neural Network consists of input layer, one or several hidden layers and an input layer as in fig 1.

Fig. 1: The structure design of BP neural network

The node action function of BP neural network is generally “S” function. Common activation function $f(x)$ is derivable sigmoid function:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (28)$$

Error function R is:

$$R = \frac{\sum (y_{mj} - y_j)^2}{2} \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (29)$$

In this formula, Y_j is expected out Y_{mj} is actual output n is sample length.

The uniform expression of weight modified formula of BP algorithm is:

$$w_{ij}^{(t+1)} = w_{ij}(t) + \eta \delta_{pj} o_{pj} \quad (30)$$

BP-IPSO Algorithm for solving reactive power dispatch problem

BP algorithm: The specific process of BP algorithm can be generalized as follows:

Step 1: Select n samples as a training set.

Step 2: Initialize weight and biases value in neural network. The initialized values are always random numbers between (-1, 1). Every sample in the training set needs the following processing:

Step 3: According to the size of every connection weight, the data of input layer are weighted and input into the activation function of hidden layer and then new values are obtained. According to the size of every connection weight, the new values are weighted and input into the activation function of output layer and the output results of output layer are calculated.

Step 4: If there exists error between output result and desired result, the calculation training is wrong.

Step 5: Adjust weight and biases value.

Step 6: According to new weight and biases values, the output layer is calculated. The calculation doesn't stop until the training set meets the stopping condition.

The improved particle swarm algorithm optimizes neural network:

The method that we apply Improved Particle Swarm Optimization to train BP Network is: improved PSO-BP algorithm is to use improved PSO algorithm to optimize the original weight and the threshold value. When the algorithm ends, we can find the point near the overall situation optimal point. On the base of improved PSO algorithm, we can use BP algorithm to search overall situation by starting from here and then achieve the network training goal. In the particle swarm, every particle's position represents weights set among the

BP network during the resent iteration. The dimension of every particle is decided by the number of the weight and the threshold value serving as connecting bridge.

The concrete process can be narrated as follows:

Step 1: Initialization: n_i is the number of neurons in the hidden layer no representing the number of neurons in input layer. So, the dimension of particle swarm D is:

$$D = n_i \times n_h + n_h \times n_o + n_h + n_o \quad (31)$$

Step 2: Setting fitness function of particle swarm' in this text, we choose mean square error in BP Neural Network as fitness function of particle swarm:

$$E = \frac{1}{M} \sum_K^m \sum_{j=1}^{n_o} (y_{kj} - \overline{y_{kj}}) \quad (32)$$

y_{kj} : The output in theory based on sample K

$\overline{y_{kj}}$: The virtual output based on sample K

M: The number of Neural Network

Step 3: Using the improved particle swarm algorithm to optimize the weight and the threshold value of BP network.

Step 4: Coming to the optimal weight and the threshold value based on formula 33:

$$g_{best} = \begin{bmatrix} h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{n_h}, o_1, o_2, \dots, o_{n_o}, ih_1, ih_2, \dots, ih_{n_i \times n_h}, \\ ho_1, ho_2, \dots, ho_{n_h \times n_o} \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

h_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n_h$): the threshold value in the hidden layer.

o_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n_o$) : The threshold value in the output layer

ih_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, n_i \times n_h$): the weight between the hidden layer and the input layer

ho_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, n_h \times n_o$) : the weight between The Hidden layer and the out layer

Step 5: Letting the optimal weight and the threshold value as the original weight and the threshold value of BP network and then

put them into Neural Network for training. Adjusting the weight and the threshold value based on BP algorithm until the function index of the network's Mean Square Error (MSE) < e. e is the preset expected index.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

The validity of the proposed Algorithm technique is demonstrated on IEEE-30 bus system. The IEEE-30 bus system has 6 generator buses, 24 load buses and 41 transmission lines of which four branches are (6-9), (6-10) , (4-12) and (28-27) - are with the tap setting transformers. The lower voltage magnitude limits at all buses are 0.95 p.u. and the upper limits are 1.1 for all the PV buses and 1.05 p.u. for all the PQ buses and the reference bus. The simulation results have been presented in Tables 1, 2, 3 &4. And in the table 5 shows clearly that proposed algorithm efficiently reduces the real power losses when compared to other given algorithms. The optimal values of the control variables along with the minimum loss obtained are given in Table 1. Equivalent to this control variable setting and it was found that there are no limit violations in any of the state variables.

TABLE1.RESULTS OF BP-IPSO – ORPD OPTIMAL CONTROL VARIABLES

Control variables	Variable setting
V1	1.041
V2	1.040
V5	1.040
V8	1.031
V11	1.010
V13	1.040
T11	1.09
T12	1.02
T15	1.1
T36	1.0
Qc10	3

Qc12	2
Qc15	4
Qc17	0
Qc20	3
Qc23	4
Qc24	3
Qc29	3
Real power loss	4.2589
SVSM	0.2465

T11	0.091
T12	0.090
T15	0.090
T36	0.090
Qc10	2
Qc12	1
Qc15	3
Qc17	2
Qc20	0
Qc23	3
Qc24	4
Qc29	4
Real power loss	4.9701
SVSM	0.2482

ORPD including voltage stability constraint problem was handled in this case as a multi-objective optimization problem where both power loss and maximum voltage stability margin of the system were optimized concurrently. Table 2 indicates the optimal values of these control variables. Also it is found that there are no limit violations of the state variables. It indicates the voltage stability index has increased to 0.2465 from 0.2482, an advance in the system voltage stability. To determine the voltage security of the system, contingency analysis was conducted using the control variable setting obtained in case 1 and case 2. The Eigen values equivalents to the four critical contingencies are given in Table 3. From this result it is observed that the Eigen value has been improved considerably for all contingencies in the second case.

TABLE 2. RESULTS OF BP-IPSO -VOLTAGE STABILITY CONTROL REACTIVE POWER DISPATCH OPTIMAL CONTROL VARIABLES

Control Variables	Variable Setting
V1	1.040
V2	1.039
V5	1.038
V8	1.029
V11	1.007
V13	1.039

TABLE 3. VOLTAGE STABILITY UNDER CONTINGENCY STATE

Sl.No	Contingency	ORPD Setting	VSCRPD Setting
1	28-27	0.1400	0.1400
2	4-12	0.1648	0.1671
3	1-3	0.1774	0.1713
4	2-4	0.2022	0.2021

TABLE 1. VOLTAGE STABILITY UNDER CONTINGENCY STATE

Sl.No	Contingency	ORPD Setting	Vscrpd Setting
1	28-27	0.1400	0.1402
2	4-12	0.1658	0.1669
3	1-3	0.1784	0.1704
4	2-4	0.2012	0.2025

TABLE 2. LIMIT VIOLATION CHECKING OF STATE VARIABLES

State variables	limits		ORPD	VSCRPD
	Lower	upper		
Q1	-20	152	1.3422	-1.3269
Q2	-20	61	8.9900	9.8232
Q5	-15	49.92	25.920	26.001
Q8	-10	63.52	38.8200	40.802
Q11	-15	42	2.9300	5.002
Q13	-15	48	8.1025	6.033
V3	0.95	1.05	1.0372	1.0392
V4	0.95	1.05	1.0307	1.0328

V6	0.95	1.05	1.0282	1.0298
V7	0.95	1.05	1.0101	1.0152
V9	0.95	1.05	1.0462	1.0412
V10	0.95	1.05	1.0482	1.0498
V12	0.95	1.05	1.0400	1.0466
V14	0.95	1.05	1.0474	1.0443
V15	0.95	1.05	1.0457	1.0413
V16	0.95	1.05	1.0426	1.0405
V17	0.95	1.05	1.0382	1.0396
V18	0.95	1.05	1.0392	1.0400
V19	0.95	1.05	1.0381	1.0394
V20	0.95	1.05	1.0112	1.0194
V21	0.95	1.05	1.0435	1.0243
V22	0.95	1.05	1.0448	1.0396
V23	0.95	1.05	1.0472	1.0372
V24	0.95	1.05	1.0484	1.0372
V25	0.95	1.05	1.0142	1.0192
V26	0.95	1.05	1.0494	1.0422
V27	0.95	1.05	1.0472	1.0452
V28	0.95	1.05	1.0243	1.0283
V29	0.95	1.05	1.0439	1.0419
V30	0.95	1.05	1.0418	1.0397

TABLE 3. COMPARISON OF REAL POWER LOSS

<i>Method</i>	<i>Minimum loss</i>
Evolutionary programming[11]	5.0159
Genetic algorithm[12]	4.665
Real coded GA with Lindex as SVSM[13]	4.568
Real coded genetic algorithm[14]	4.5015
Proposed BP-IPSO method	4.2589

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper a novel approach BP-IPSO algorithm used to solve optimal reactive power dispatch problem, considering various generator constraints, has been successfully applied. The performance of the proposed algorithm demonstrated through its voltage stability assessment by modal analysis is effective at various instants following system contingencies. Also this method has a good performance for voltage stability Enhancement of large, complex power system networks. The effectiveness of the proposed method is demonstrated on IEEE 30-bus system.

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